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“SIPALAY CITY “THE JEWEL OF THE SUGAR ISLAND” THAT BECAME MY HOME”

It's been six years ago, when I was first assigned as a College Instructor in Central Philippines State University Sipalay Campus, I had no idea how much this beautiful and majestic place would become a part of me. Sipalay City was called the "Jewel of the Sugar Island", is not just a picturesque coastal city in the southern part of Negros Occidental. It is a paradise for tranquility, natural beauty, and a place where I discovered the true meaning of peace.

From the moment I arrived, I was struck by the serenity that Sipalay City offers. The white sandy shore of the beach front, with its gentle waves and stunning horizon, I felt like stepping in Boracay island. The soft rustle of the coconut trees and the crystal-clear waters immediately made me feel at home. If I am bored and stressed from my work, I always visited the beach front to feel the calmness by simply looking the beautiful sunset.

Sipalay City is much more than just a tourist destination alone, it is also a place that teaches the importance of environmental sustainability. The people of Sipalay City also deeply care about the environment. I witnessed firsthand how Sipalaynons actively engage in preserving the natural beauty of their city- like coastal clean-up drives, mangrove and tree planting activities which I always love to join. I was amazed and inspired by the dedication of the Local Government Unit of Sipalay City and all Sipalaynons who worked tirelessly just to ensure that the future generations would be able to experience the same beauty I had come to love.

Spending my time in Sipalay City was a journey for personal growth. I learned as much from the city as I did from my college students. The stillness and beauty of the place taught me to slow down, to appreciate small and simple things, and to more mindful of the world around me. Sipalay City became my sanctuary- a place for peace and meditation where I could reconnect with nature and find balance in my life. It is a city that reminded me of the importance of environment.

Sipalay City is not just a part of Negros Occidental; it is a part of me now, and I know that no matter where my teaching career takes me, I will always find peace in the memories of Sipalay City, the Jewel of the Sugar Island which I called my home.